

New formulations of topological indices in Triangular Benzenoid

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ABSTRACT

In this article, triangular benzenoid is considered. The SMP-polynomial for the structure is obtained and using that polynomial, closed formulas for some distance-based indices are computed. These formulas are presented in terms of the number of hexagons in the base of the graph. Hence indices can be calculated via new formulas without counting the degrees of the vertices and partitioning the edges. Finally, the results are displayed numerically and graphically.

Keywords: Molecular graph, Triangular benzenoid, SMP-polynomial, Topological index.

1. INTRODUCTION

Benzenoid systems are important structures in theoretical chemistry. A benzenoid system is an infinite hexagonal or honeycomb network with a finite and connected planar subgraph without cut vertices, and each interior face is a regular hexagon. These compounds, known as hydrocarbons, are composed primarily of carbon and hydrogen atoms and contain one or more benzene rings, see Figure 1. Some of them are monocyclic for example, benzene (C_6H_6), which is the simplest member of the class, and some are polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). These contain two or more fused benzene rings, for example, Pyrene ($C_{19}H_{12}$) with four fused benzene rings. In addition to the food industry, they can be used as industrial solvents or as raw materials for synthesizing various chemicals, including plastics, dyes, and pharmaceuticals [1, 2]. Mathematical chemistry is an important intersection between mathematics and chemistry that uses mathematical tools to predict and analyze chemical structures and properties. Among the branches of mathematical chemistry is graph theory, which helps determine the properties of chemical compounds based on their molecular graphs by modeling chemical structures using graphs and developing topological indices (TIs) [3, 4]. A TI is a number that describes the topology of a chemical structure. They are known as tools for predicting the chemical and biological properties of chemical structures and assessing the topological similarity between chemical structures. They are particularly helpful for isomer discrimination, structure-property relationships, structure-activity relationships, and drug design in chemistry, biochemistry, and nanotechnology [5]. TIs are classified into several categories, including degree-based TIs, distance-based TIs, and connection number-based TIs [7]. In 1947, Wiener introduced the concept of TIs in his work, specifically defining the Wiener index. He established a significant correlation between this index and the boiling points of alkanes, demonstrating its utility in predicting chemical properties based on molecular structure [6]. Some of the distance-based TIs are the Szeged (Sz), Mostar (Mo), and Padmakar-Ivan (PI) indices. The Sz index is the oldest TI based on distance and is as follows [8]:

$$Sz(G) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(G)} n_u(e|G)n_v(e|G).$$

The Mo used as a measure of peripherality in chemical graphs, is defined as:

$$Mo(G) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(G)} |n_u(e|G) - n_v(e|G)|.$$

Khadikar introduced the vertex PI index as follows:

$$PI(G) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(G)} (n_u(e|G)n + n_v(e|G)).$$

In mathematical chemistry, algebraic polynomials play an essential role in calculating TIs [9]. In 2015, Deutsch and Klavžar introduced a polynomial called the M-polynomial [10, 11]. This polynomial is the most general algebraic polynomial for obtaining a large number of degree-based TIs [12].

In 2023, Knor and Tratnik introduced the SMP-polynomial. The SMP polynomial is a polynomial that has two variables and can be easily used to calculate three Sz, Mo, and PI. The SMP-polynomial of G is written as:

$$SMP(G; x, y) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(G), n_u(e|G) \geq n_v(e|G)} x^{n_u(e|G)} y^{n_v(e|G)}.$$

where $n_u(e|G) = |N_u(e|G)|$ and $N_u(e|G) = \{x \in V(G) \mid d_G(x, u) < d_G(x, v)\}$ are number and set of vertices of G lying closer to u, respectively [8].

In the next section, triangular benzenoid is investigated. The SMP-polynomials have been calculated for the structure. New formulas for Sz, Mo, and PI indices are obtained. These formulas are in terms of the number of hexagons at the base of the graph. As a result, there is no need to count the degrees of the vertices and partition the edges to calculate these indices. Also, the relationship between the new formulas for the indices is found. The values of the indices for the benzenoid systems are calculated for $r = 1, \dots, 6$. The results are displayed numerically and graphically.

2. Main results

In this article, the r-dimensional triangular benzenoid graph is denoted by the symbol T_r , where r is the number of hexagons in the base of the graph, see Figure 1. T_r has $n = |V(T_r)| = r^2 + 4r + 1$ vertices and $m = |E(T_r)| = \frac{3}{2}r(r + 3)$ edges. Edge partitioning of the T_r graph is given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Triangular benzenoid T_r .

Table 1. Edge partition of T_r , when $1 \leq i \leq r$.

$\{n_u, n_v\}$	$\{n - (i(i+2)), i(i+2)\}$	Total edges
Number of Edges	$3(i+1)$	$\frac{3}{2}r(r+3)$

Table 2 includes some distance-based TIs computed via SMP-polynomial, where the operators used are defined as:

$$D_x \text{SMP}(G; x, y) = x \left(\frac{\partial \text{SMP}}{\partial x} \right),$$

$$D_y \text{SMP}(G; x, y) = y \left(\frac{\partial \text{SMP}}{\partial y} \right).$$

Table 2. Derivation of some TIs from SMP-polynomial.

TI	Derivative from SMP ($G; x, y$)
Sz index	$D_x D_y (\text{SMP}(G; x, y)) _{x=y=1}$
Mo index	$D_x (\text{SMP}(G; x, \frac{1}{x})) _{x=1}$
PI index	$D_x (\text{SMP}(G; x, x)) _{x=1}$

These TIs can be calculated using SMP-polynomial and Table 2. In this work, formulas are presented to calculate these indices based on the number of hexagons in the base of the graph.

Theorem 2.1: Consider Triangular benzenoid. Then, its SMP-polynomial is as follows:

$$\text{SMP}(T_r; x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1) x^{n-i(i+2)} y^{i(i+2)}.$$

Proof: We can calculate the SMP-polynomial of phenacenes using Figure 1 and Table 1 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SMP}(T_r; x, y) &= \sum_{n_u(e) \geq n_v(e)} x^{n_u(e)} y^{n_v(e)} |G| \\ &= |E_{\{n-3,3\}}| x^{n-3} y^3 + |E_{\{n-8,8\}}| x^{n-8} y^8 + \dots + |E_{\{n-(r(r+2)), r(r+2)\}}| x^{n-(r(r+2))} y^{r(r+2)} \\ &= 6 x^{n-3} y^3 + 9 x^{n-8} y^8 + \dots \\ &\quad + 3(r+1) x^{n-(r(r+2))} y^{r(r+2)} \sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1) x^{n-i(i+2)} y^{i(i+2)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 2.2: Let the structure of T_r , with $n = r^2 + 4r + 1$. Then the following hold:

Sz index: $\text{Sz}(T_r) = \sum_{i=1}^r 3i(i+1)(i+2)(n - i^2 - 2i),$

Mo index: $\text{Mo}(T_r) = \sum_{i=1}^r |n - 2i(i+2)|,$

PI index: $\text{PI}(T_r) = n \sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1).$

Proof: Let $\text{SMP}(T_r; x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1) x^{n-i(i+2)} y^{i(i+2)}$. Applying the operators to the polynomial, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} D_y \text{SMP}(T_r; x, y) &= \sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1)(i(i+2)) x^{i(i+2)-1} y^{n-(i(i+2))}, \\ D_x D_y \text{SMP}(T_r; x, y) &= \sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1)(i(i+2))(n - (i(i+2))) x^{i(i+2)-1} y^{n-(i(i+2))-1}, \\ D_x \left(\text{SMP} \left(T_r; x, \frac{1}{x} \right) \right) &= \sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1) |n - 2(i(i+2))| x^{n-2(i(i+2))}, \end{aligned}$$

$$D_x(SMP(T_r; x, x)) = \sum_{i=1}^r 3n(i+1)x^n.$$

Then due to Table 2, we conclude that:

$$\begin{aligned} Sz(T_r) &= \sum_{i=1}^r 3i(i+1)(i+2)(n-i^2-2i). \\ Mo(T_r) &= \sum_{i=1}^r |n-2i(i+2)|. \\ PI(T_r) &= n\sum_{i=1}^r 3(i+1). \end{aligned}$$

The numerical values of these TIs for $r = 1, \dots, 6$ are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Numerical comparison of Sz, Mo, and PI.

r	1	2	3	4	5	6
$Sz(T_r)$	54	540	2610	8820	23940	121464
$Mo(T_r)$	0	69	246	576	1164	2199
$PI(T_r)$	36	195	594	1386	2760	4941

Considering that the value of r increases gradually, it can be seen from Figure 2 that all the indices are increasing.

Fig. 2. Graphical comparison of TIs.

3. Conclusion

In this article, closed formulas of distance-based topological indices such as the Sz index, Mo index, and PI index of triangular benzenoid are presented. These formulas are independent of counting edges. They are presented based on the number of hexagons at the base of the graph. The obtained results are displayed graphically and numerically. It is shown that with the increase of r -value, the topological indices also increase. The Sz and Mo indices have the highest and lowest values for the triangular benzenoid, respectively.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] K. Sharma, V. K. Bhat, J. B. Liu, *Second leap hyper-Zagreb coindex of certain benzenoid structures and their polynomials*, *Computational and Theoretical Chemistry* 1223 (2023) 114088.
- [2] L. Amir, M. Saheli, *Computing two types of geometric-arithmetic indices of some benzenoid graphs*, *J. Discrete Math Its App* 8. 3 (2023) 171–175.
- [3] Afzal, F., Razaq, M. A., Razaq, M. A., Afzal, D., Hameed, S. *Weighted entropy of penta chains graph*. *Eurasian Chemical Communications*, 2(6), (2020) 652-662.
- [4] Amin, S., Rehman, M.A., Farahani, M.R., Cancan, M., Aldemir, M. S. *Multiplicative degree-based topological indices and line graph of hex board graph*. *Eurasian Chem. Commun*, 2(11) (2020) 1137-1145.
- [5] E. Deutsch, S. Klavzar, *M-polynomial and degree-based topological indices*, *arXiv preprint arXiv: 1407.1592* (2014).
- [6] Z. Rajabinejad, S. Mohammadian Semnani. "Calculation of topological indices based on Mpolynomial for Polytrimethylene terephthalate." *Journal of Discrete Mathematics and Its Applications* 9, no. 3 (2024): 181-190.
- [7] Sattar, Aqsa, and Muhammad Javaid. "On Comparing Rhombus Oxide and Silicate Networks via Zagreb Connection Indices." *Punjab University Journal of Mathematics* 56, no. 1-2 (2024): 31-50.
- [8] Z. Rajabinejad, S. Mohammadian-Semnani, *Calculation of topological indices based on the distance of polyacenes without edge counting*, *Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds* (2023) 1–12, doi:10.1080/10406638.2023.2276244.
- [9] M. Nadeem, M. A. Alam, N. Ali, M. I. Elashiry, *An Algebraic Approach of Topological Indices Connected with Finite Quasigroups*, *J. Function Spaces*. 14 (2024) 1948465.
- [10] E. Deutsch, S. Klavžar, *M-polynomial and degree-based topological indices*, *Iranian J. Math. Chem*. 6 (2015) 93–102.
- [11] M. Ajmal, W. Nazeer, M. Munir, S. M. Kang, C. Y. Jung, *The M-Polynomials and topological indices of generalized prism network*, *Int. J. Math. Anal*. 11 (2017) 293–303.
- [12] R.S. Haoer, *Topological indices of metal-organic networks via neighborhood M-polynomial*, *J. Discrete Math. Sci. Cryptogr*. 24 (2), 369–390 (2021), doi:10.1080/09720529.2021.1888433.